

Copper(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes of Isatin-3, 2'-Quinolylhydrazones

R. C. KHULBE, Y. K. BHOON and R. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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Complexes of the general composition $[M^{II}(L-H)Cl]$ where $M = Cu^{II}$ or Ni^{II} and $L =$ Isatin-3,2'-quinolylhydrazone (IQH) or N-methylisatin-3,2'-quinolylhydrazone (MIQH) have been prepared and characterized by magnetic susceptibility, electronic and ir spectral measurements. Magnetic measurements in the temperature range (300-4°K) are confirmative of magnetically dilute tetrahedral geometry for nickel(II) complexes. Zero field splitting has been inferred from this data.

In view of their high selectivity and specificity for different metal ions terdentate ligands having a heterocyclic atom, an azo group and phenolic group ortho to azo position have been extensively investigated as analytical reagents¹. It is only recently that the 3d-metal complexes of such a class of compounds have been studied by the authors to elucidate the electronic structures²⁻⁸ by ESR, magnetic susceptibility measurements at different temperatures, electronic spectra and mass spectra. In order to study the effect of steric hindrance imposed by the bulky structural ligands which may give either planar or tetrahedral complexes, isatin-3, 2'-quinolylhydrazone (IQH) and N-methylisatin-3, 2'-quinolylhydrazone (MIQH) were synthesized and the present communication describes the magnetic and spectral properties of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes of these compounds.

Experimental

Preparation of ligands and complexes : IQH and MIQH were prepared by the condensation of 2-hydrazinoquinoline with isatin or N-methylisatin. The details are given below :

(i) *Preparation of 2-hydrazinoquinoline* : 2-Chloroquinoline (12 g) and hydrazine hydrate (99.9%) (40 ml) were refluxed for 2 hrs. The orange coloured liquid was distilled under reduced pressure to remove excess hydrazine hydrate. The residue obtained on cooling the concentrated liquid was mixed with hot water, filtered and washed three to four times with hot water and dried in air. It was recrystallized from dry benzene to get scarlet crystals of 2-hydrazinoquinoline (m.p. 142-143°).

(ii) *Preparation of IQH and MIQH* : Equimolar quantities of 2-hydrazinoquinoline and isatin/N-methylisatin were dissolved in alcohol, 5 ml glacial acetic acid added to the clear solution and the reaction mixture refluxed for 3-4 hrs. The compounds precipitated out as fine granules, which were filtered, washed with cold alcohol and recrystallized from benzene and alcohol respectively.

(iii) *Preparation of complexes* : Copper(II) complexes : Equimolar quantities of copper(II) chloride and IQH or MIQH were dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol and mixed together. A brown precipitate was obtained in each case, which was filtered, washed successively with alcohol and ether and dried over P_4O_{10} under vacuum.

Nickel(II) complexes with IQH : Equimolar quantities of nickel(II) chloride and IQH were dissolved separately in minimum amount of alcohol. Refluxing the solution for about 2 hrs resulted in the precipitation of the yellow compound which was filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and dried over P_4O_{10} under vacuum.

Nickel(II) complex with MIQH : For precipitation of the complex the pH of the resulting solution obtained by mixing equimolar quantities of nickel(II) chloride and MIQH was essentially to be raised by adding diluted NaOH solution. The dark brown precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed successively with alcohol, ether and dried over P_4O_{10} under vacuum.

Physical measurements : The magnetic measurements at room temperature were carried out using a Gouy balance using $Hg [Co(CNS)_4]$ as the calibrant ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ cgs). However, the susceptibility measurements upto 4°K for $[Ni(MIQH-H)Cl]$ were carried out by the earlier described SQUID susceptometer⁹.

NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian 60-NMR spectrometer. Absorption spectra were measured on Cary-14 and Cφ-10 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating ir spectrophotometer.

The compounds were analysed for C, H and N in the Microanalytical Laboratory, CIBA-GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay. Metal contents were determined by usual methods.

Results and Discussion

The results of the elemental analysis for the compounds are presented in Table 1.

TABLE I—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA

Compound	%M Calcd. (Found)	%C Calcd. (Found)	%N Calcd. (Found)	%H Calcd. (Found)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
IQH	—	70.8 (70.5)	19.5 (18.9)	4.17 (4.20)	—
MIQH	—	71.5 (71.7)	18.6 (18.8)	4.6 (4.3)	—
[Cu ^{II} (IQH-H)Cl]	16.45 (16.60)	52.80 (52.80)	14.52 (14.60)	2.90 (3.10)	1.70
[Cu ^{II} (MIQH-H)Cl]	15.19 (14.90)	53.60 (53.40)	14.70 (14.80)	2.80 (3.10)	1.83
[Ni ^{II} (IQH-H)Cl]	14.89 (14.70)	54.40 (54.90)	14.20 (14.50)	3.28 (3.30)	3.81
[Ni ^{II} (MIQH-H)Cl]	14.90 (15.00)	54.67 (54.50)	14.20 (14.15)	3.29 (3.50)	3.76

Characterization of IQH and MIQH: The synthesized ligands IQH and MIQH have been characterized by elemental analysis and ir and nmr spectral data. Though IQH and MIQH are very complex molecules, the ir spectra of the compounds are sufficiently informative to prove the keto-enol tautomerism in the molecules.

The broad band in the region $3500-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is assigned to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ of the enolic form. The broadening of the band in the present cases could be due to the hydrogen bonding in the molecules. These findings have a support from the nmr spectrum of MIQH recorded in CDCl_3 (due to low solubility of IQH in CDCl_3 the spectrum could not be recorded) which has an enolic proton signal at -3.67τ in the low field region. The hydroxylic proton is usually observed at -5.00τ . The lowering in the present case is due to the strong hydrogen bonding as has been observed earlier in similar type of compounds¹⁰. The nmr data together with ir data are confirmative of the following type of keto-enol tautomerism in IQH and MIQH.

Since there was no effect on the position of $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ on dilution, it was inferred that intramolecular hydrogen bonding was present in the molecules.

The elemental analysis of the complexes correspond to the general formula $[\text{M}^{\text{II}}(\text{L}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$ where

$\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ and $\text{L} = \text{IQH}, \text{MIQH}$. Conductance measurements carried out in nitrobenzene are indicative of non-electrolytic nature of the complexes, thus confirming the participation of chloride ion in all the complexes in the coordination sphere. The coordination number four is thus concluded for both copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes.

Copper(II) complexes, irrespective of the stereochemistry involved, contain one unpaired electron per copper atom and show magnetic moment in the range 1.75-2.20 B. M. unless there are major interactions between the unpaired electrons on different copper ions. Spin-spin interactions lead to subnormal magnetic moment values showing marked temperature dependence. Susceptibility measurements on copper(II) complexes yield normal value (1.83 B.M.) for $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{MIQH}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$ but a slightly lower value (1.70 B.M.) for $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{IQH}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$. Axial interactions leading to slight lowering in magnetic moment in $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{IQH}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$ could be inferred in view of the planar stereochemistry which is not possible in $[\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}(\text{MIQH}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$ due to the obvious steric hindrance of N-methyl group. Tetrahedral geometry could be excluded since aggregation of molecules would lead to an unfavourable geometry. The planar geometry for the complexes gains support from the fact that there

is a marked and distinct change in the colour from brown to greenish by the addition of dioxane followed by heating, possibly due to the axial coordination of the solvent molecules leading to the octahedral geometry in each case.

Magnetically, all nickel(II) complexes may be of two types, having either two unpaired electrons or no unpaired electrons. In the first category fall the complexes with six coordinate octahedral, five coordinate square pyramidal, four coordinate tetrahedral geometries and in the second category, those with five coordinate trigonal bipyramidal and square planar geometries. Since the nickel(II) complexes under study are paramagnetic, from among the structures mentioned above only those of high spin type are left for consideration. Five coordinate is rather unusual in nickel(II) complexes and when encountered, exists as a result of particular circumstances in the complex rather than because of any intrinsic tendency on the part of nickel(II) ion to attain the structure. In fact, qualitative arguments show that tetrahedral and octahedral configurations are more stable than the five coordinate ones. A choice, only between a six coordinate octahedral and four coordinate tetrahedral structure for the complexes is thus left. In the octahedral complex the magnetic moment values lie between 2.9-3.3 B.M. and are almost temperature independent. The ground term in tetrahedral complexes ${}^3T_1(F)$ is orbitally triply degenerate and magnetic moment of such complexes is expected to contain some orbital contribution which raises the magnetic moment values as high as 4.1 B. M. At room temperature, the tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes always show μ_{eff} values more than 3.3 B. M. usually ranging from 3.4-3.9 B. M., which are temperature dependent and the drop in the magnetic moment with lowering of the temperature is dependent upon the symmetry of the complex^{11,12}. The magnetic moment values obtained in the nickel(II) complexes under study also lie in this range and thus octahedral geometry may be ruled out. The temperature dependence of the magnetic moment has been checked in $[\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}(\text{MIQH}-\text{H})\text{Cl}]$ by carrying out measurements upto 4°K. The complex obeys Curie law down to 4°K which is indicative of magnetically dilute nature of the complex (Fig. 1). The drop in magnetic moment below 10°K is due to the zero field splitting caused by the asymmetric ligand field. However, the rise in the magnetic moment above 10°K is slightly puzzling. The drop in the magnetic moment value of 3.76 B. M. at room temperature to 3.20 B. M. at 70°K (Fig. 2) is the one expected for tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes with highly asymmetric structure¹¹.

As the ligand absorbs in the visible region, the bands appearing in the visible spectra of the complexes are assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the azo group of the ligand molecule which has undergone a red shift on complexation. The methanolic solution of copper(II) complexes when heated with dioxane develop green colour which shows a

Fig. 1 μ_{eff} vs T graph
band at 14710 cm^{-1} assignable to $T_{2g} \rightarrow E_g$ in the octahedral copper(II) complex resulted, due to the axial coordination of the dioxane molecules as represented below. Due to the absorption of the

ligands at 600-300 cm^{-1} , it was difficult to trace out $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-C}_1}$ bands in the complexes. Thus on the basis of the magnetic susceptibility and absorption spectra planar geometry for copper(II) and tetrahedral structure for the nickel(II) complexes are assigned.

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References

1. S. SHIBATA in "Chelates in Analytical Chemistry", Ed., H. A. FLASCHKA and A. J. BARNARD, Vol. IV, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1972.
2. Y. K. BHOON, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 907.
3. Y. K. BHOON, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 681.
4. Y. K. BHOON, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1976, **6**, 71.
5. Y. K. BHOON, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.* 1977, **15A**, 1019.
6. Y. K. BHOON, R. P. SINGH and A. K. GREGSON, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1979, **9**, 251.
7. Y. K. BHOON and R. P. SINGH, *Annali di Chimica*, 1979, **69**, 477.
8. Y. K. BHOON, K. B. PANDEYA and R. P. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 286.
9. A. K. GREGSON, P. C. HEALY and D. M. DODDRELL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 1216.
10. D. BRITTON and D. JOHN, *Analyst*, 1973, **98**, 377.
11. B. N. FIGGIS, J. LEWIS, F. MABBS and G. A. WEBB, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966A, 1411.
12. L. SACCONI, M. CIAMPOLINI and U. CAMPIGILI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 407.